

The role of ecosystem transpiration in creating alternate moisture regimes by influencing atmospheric moisture convergence

Anastassia M. Makarieva^{1,2}, Andrei V. Nefiodov², Antonio Donato Nobre³, Mara Baudena⁴, Ugo Bardi⁵, Douglas Sheil^{6,7,8}, Scott R. Saleska⁹, Ruben D. Molina¹⁰, and Anja Rammig¹¹

¹Institute for Advanced Study, Technical University of Munich, Lichtenbergstrasse 2 a, 85748 Garching, Germany

²Theoretical Physics Division, Petersburg Nuclear Physics Institute, 188300 Gatchina, St. Petersburg, Russia

³Centro de Ciência do Sistema Terrestre INPE, São José dos Campos, 12227-010 São Paulo, Brazil

⁴National Research Council of Italy, Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC), Torino, Italy

⁵Department of Chemistry, University of Florence, Italy

⁶Forest Ecology and Forest Management Group, Wageningen University & Research, PO Box 47, 6700 AA, Wageningen, The Netherlands

⁷Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR), Kota Bogor, Jawa Barat, 16115, Indonesia

⁸Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Natural Resource Management, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Ås, Norway

⁹Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Arizona, Tucson, 85721, Arizona, USA

¹⁰Escuela Ambiental, Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín, Colombia

¹¹Technical University of Munich, School of Life Sciences, Hans-Carl-von-Carlowitz-Platz 2, 85354 Freising, Germany

Correspondence: A. D. Nobre (anobre27@gmail.com), A. M. Makarieva (ammakarieva@gmail.com)

Supplementary Information

Table S1: This table reports the i -th percentiles q_i , the mean ($\bar{P}$) and the standard deviations (sd) of the distribution of hourly precipitation (mm/hour) in the Amazon study area of Baudena et al. (2021), between 0–18°S and 50–65°W (Fig. 4). The analyses were performed for the period 2003–2014 at 0.25° resolution. Hourly precipitation and column water vapor (W) are from the ERA5 dataset (Hersbach et al., 2018). Precipitation was binned for different values of W , every millimeter of W . For each bin, we calculated the precipitation percentiles only if there were more than five points in the bin, from $W = 3$ mm up to the maximum retained value of $W = 73$ mm.

W bin	q_1	q_{10}	q_{25}	q_{50}	q_{75}	q_{90}	q_{99}	$\bar{P}$	sd
3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01
5	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
7	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00
9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01
10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.01
11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.01
12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.01
13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.01
14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.02
15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.02
16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.02
17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.02
18	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.02
19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.02
20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.03
21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.03
22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.03
23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.04
24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.05
25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.05
26	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.06
27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.07
28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.08
29	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.08
30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.09
31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.01	0.09
32	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.01	0.09
33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.01	0.10

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Table S1 – continued from previous page

W bin	q_1	q_{10}	q_{25}	q_{50}	q_{75}	q_{90}	q_{99}	$\bar{P}$	sd
34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17	0.01	0.10
35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.20	0.01	0.10
36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.25	0.01	0.12
37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.30	0.02	0.13
38	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.38	0.02	0.15
39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.48	0.03	0.17
40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.60	0.03	0.19
41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.08	0.77	0.04	0.23
42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.09	0.99	0.05	0.26
43	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.12	1.27	0.07	0.30
44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.15	1.54	0.08	0.34
45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.19	1.85	0.10	0.39
46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.24	2.20	0.12	0.44
47	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.31	2.53	0.15	0.50
48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.10	0.40	2.85	0.18	0.56
49	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.12	0.52	3.16	0.21	0.61
50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.16	0.64	3.42	0.24	0.66
51	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.20	0.78	3.64	0.28	0.71
52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.24	0.91	3.83	0.32	0.76
53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.30	1.05	4.01	0.36	0.80
54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.37	1.19	4.17	0.40	0.84
55	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.10	0.46	1.34	4.36	0.45	0.89
56	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.13	0.55	1.50	4.55	0.51	0.95
57	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.18	0.66	1.66	4.78	0.57	1.01
58	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.23	0.79	1.84	5.05	0.65	1.08
59	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.29	0.93	2.03	5.39	0.73	1.17
60	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.36	1.09	2.26	5.92	0.84	1.30
61	0.00	0.01	0.10	0.45	1.28	2.54	6.79	0.98	1.48
62	0.00	0.01	0.13	0.56	1.50	2.90	8.29	1.15	1.74
63	0.00	0.02	0.19	0.71	1.79	3.40	10.72	1.41	2.12
64	0.00	0.04	0.26	0.91	2.20	4.23	13.89	1.78	2.66
65	0.00	0.07	0.37	1.19	2.77	5.70	16.98	2.32	3.35
66	0.00	0.12	0.51	1.57	3.71	8.39	20.25	3.11	4.23
67	0.00	0.18	0.77	2.25	5.55	11.71	22.72	4.23	5.15
68	0.00	0.26	1.07	3.37	8.40	14.70	25.11	5.65	6.07
69	0.00	0.28	1.36	4.95	11.26	16.95	26.27	7.05	6.75
70	0.03	0.56	2.19	6.64	13.38	19.64	29.85	8.60	7.60
71	0.02	0.75	2.76	10.29	15.52	21.23	29.22	10.26	7.76
72	0.04	0.52	3.15	11.37	17.13	20.40	28.52	10.62	7.61
73	0.07	0.10	0.17	0.78	2.30	29.90	35.50	6.29	11.89

Table S2. Characteristic precipitation P (mm/year), mean trends (mm/year²) and their confidence intervals (in brackets) for precipitation dP/dt , evapotranspiration dE/dt and runoff dR/dt in world regions with different precipitation regimes, data taken from Fig. 2 of Hobeichi et al. (2022), time period 1980–2012; k_P/k_E calculated as the ratio of dP/dt and dE/dt .

Regime	P	dP/dt	dE/dt	dR/dt	k_P/k_E
“Extremely wet, low variability”	4000	12.5 (4.4–22)	0.43 (0–1)	10.3 (5.8–15)	29
“Very wet, low variability”	2900	6.7 (2.2–11)	0.55 (0.24–0.96)	6.9 (3.0–11)	12
“Wet, low variability”	2200	3.8 (0.49–8.5)	0.6 (0.28–1.0)	3.5 (0.94–6.4)	6.3
“Wet, medium variability”	1600	NS	NS	NS	
“Mild wet, medium variability”	1200	NS	0.3 (0.04–0.57)	NS	
“Mild dry, medium variability”	860	NS	0.54 (0.25–0.75)	NS	
“Dry, medium variability”	560	0.68 (0.08–1.3)	0.43 (0.09–0.7)	NS	1.6
“Dry, high variability”	325	0.45 (0.01–0.95)	NS	0.2 (0.04–0.34)	
“Very dry, very high variability”	125	NS	NS	0.06 (0–0.12)	

Abbreviation: NS, no significant trend.

In Fig. S1, to approximate the Northern and Southern Amazon regions from Baker et al.’s (2021) Figs. S12, we used basin polygons from HydroBASINS (Lehner and Grill, 2013). For the Amazon basin up to the Óbidos station, we used the polygon from the Global Runoff Data Base (https://www.bafg.de/GRDC/EN/02_srvcs/22_gslrs/gislayers_node.html). For geoprocessing, we used geopandas (Ver. 0.12.2; Jordahl et al., 2022) to select and join the HydroBASINS vector data, xarray (Ver. 2022.12.0; Hoyer et al., 2022) and rioxarray (Ver. 0.13.2; Snow et al., 2022a) to load and subset the ERA5 raster data, and geocube (Ver. 0.3.3; Snow et al., 2022b) to rasterize the regions into the ERA5 data grid. The Óbidos mask has 1534 cells (the bounding box spans from latitudes -21 to $+6$ and longitudes -80 to -55). The Southern mask has 681 cells (the bounding box spans from latitudes -21 to -3 and longitudes -73 to -50). The Northern mask has 286 cells (the bounding box spans from latitudes -4 to $+6$ and longitudes -77 to -51).

The quantities σ_E , σ_W and σ_P , discussed in Section 3.4, represent month-to-month variability:

$$\sigma_X^2 = \frac{1}{11} \sum_{i=1}^{12} (X_i - \bar{X})^2, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where X_i is the value of X in the i -th month as shown in Fig. S1, $\bar{X}$ is the mean annual value, $X = \{E, W, P\}$ and $P = C + E$. According to ERA5 data, the mean annual precipitation values $\bar{P}$ are 2800 mm/year, 2050 mm/year and 2500 mm/year for Northern, Southern and Óbidos, respectively. The corresponding mean annual atmospheric moisture content $\bar{W}$ and evapotranspiration $\bar{E}$ values are 49.7 mm, 41.9 mm and 45.5 mm and 1080 mm/year, 1260 mm/year and 1250 mm/year, respectively.

Figure S1. Seasonal climatology of evapotranspiration E , atmospheric moisture content W and atmospheric moisture convergence C in different parts of the Amazon basin for 2003–2013: “Northern” (green color in the map, comprises Japurá, Negro, Branco, and Jari river basins), “Southern” (brownish color in the map, comprises Purus, Madeira, Aripuanã, Tapajós, and Xingu river basins) and “Óbidos” (blue contour in the map, gauged at Óbidos, represents approximately 70% of the Amazon basin), see Table S1 and Fig. 1 of Baker et al. (2021). Monthly W (assessed as total column water vapor) was computed from the “ensemble_mean” and “ensemble_spread” products in the “reanalysis-era5-single-levels” ERA5 dataset (<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47>). First the time-aggregated dataset was calculated (monthly averages of 3-hourly values), then the basin mask (Southern, Northern, Óbidos) was used to compute spatial averages at each monthly step. Uncertainties represent maximum ensemble spread for the corresponding month in the period 2003–2013. Moisture convergence C calculated from the catchment balance data of Baker et al. (2021): for Óbidos, $C = R + dG/dt$, R and dG/dt are taken, respectively, from Baker et al.’s (2021) Figs. S3b and S3c (the uncertainty equals the square root of the sum of squared uncertainties for R and dG/dt); for Northern and Southern parts, $C = P - E$, where P was retrieved from ERA5 similarly to W , while E (assessed from the catchment balance) taken from Fig. S12 of Baker et al. (2021), uncertainties shown represent the uncertainties in E that in the catchment balance assessment exceed those of C (see Baker et al., 2021, Table S1), E for Óbidos, Northern and Southern are, respectively, from Figs. S3d, S12a and S12b of Baker et al. (2021).

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